

Cybersecurity Strategies for Marine Electronic Control Units

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Abstract—The rise of digital technologies has led to cyber-physical systems that seamlessly integrate engineering systems with their digital counterparts. The Internet of Things (IoT) serves as a key infrastructure for these technologies, significantly impacting the maritime sector through the demand for increased connectivity. This introduces challenges in implementing advanced networking, communication protocols, and centralized cloud connectivity. However, increased connectivity heightens cybersecurity risks, necessitating secure transmission systems. In the maritime sector the internal primary communication protocol between Electronic Control Unit (ECU) is the Controller Area Network (CAN) while external cloud connectivity is typically established by other protocols such as GSM/machine-type communication (MTC). This paper examines cybersecurity threats in maritime applications, analyzing their vulnerabilities to highlight the need for robust cybersecurity frameworks, intrusion detection systems, and data encryption. Rule-based cybersecurity algorithms are developed and validated on a small-scale test system with CAN network nodes connected to the cloud. This strategy contribute to secure the maritime sector, reducing operational risks in highly connected future systems.

Index Terms—CAN (Controller Area Network), Cloud, Cyber Security, IoT, Connected ships.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the rapidly evolving landscape of modern engineering, connectivity has become a critical enabler of system integration and operational efficiency, particularly with the widespread adoption of cloud-based infrastructures. Across multiple sectors, cloud connectivity facilitates real-time data exchange and supports decision-making processes within globally distributed digital ecosystems. The maritime industry is undergoing a similar transformation. In parallel, the concept of decarbonization of waterborne vessels has gained significant momentum, driven by increasingly stringent global environmental regulations introduced by the International Maritime Organization (IMO). Notably, since 2023, the implementation of regulatory measures such as the Energy Efficiency Existing Ship Index (EEXI) and the Carbon Intensity Indicator (CII) has underscored the urgent need for low-emission and energy-efficient vessel operations [1], [2], [3]. As a result, there is a marked acceleration toward the electrification of marine propulsion systems, accompanied by a substantial increase in the deployment of electronic control units (ECUs) and interconnected subsystems. Modern vessels, leveraging satel-

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the shipboard cybersecurity threats, highlighting access points for hackers.

lite communication and cloud platforms, are now capable of seamless real-time data transmission, enabling advanced functionalities such as predictive maintenance, fleet-wide performance optimization, and automated operational decision-making. This connectivity enables boats to transmit real-time data on operational status, navigation systems, engine performance, cargo conditions, and shipboard safety systems to centralized monitoring platforms. Through the integration of IoT (Internet of Things), vessels can receive up-to-date information such as weather forecasts, navigational hazards, and regulatory updates, enabling them to react proactively to dynamic maritime conditions. Thereto, this connectivity also exposes to a growing range of cybersecurity threats, making them attractive targets for malicious outsiders. The complexity, heterogeneity, and wireless nature of IoT networks require robust security frameworks to safeguard both operational efficiency and environmental safety [4], [5]. One of the critical components of modern ships is the ECU (Electronic Control Unit), which manages various onboard systems such as propulsion, navigation, and safety mechanisms. These ECUs are

increasingly connected to the cloud (through GSM, machine type communication (MTC), and often communicate through the CAN (Controller Area Network) protocol, a widely used but inherently insecure communication standard originally designed for automotive applications [6], [7].

Figure 1 illustrates an automated and interconnected shipboard system, highlighting potential vulnerabilities that cybercriminals could exploit. In such a scenario, malicious actors may leverage network connections to manipulate critical functions, disrupt vessel operations, or exfiltrate sensitive data. These threats can manifest as cyberattacks that trigger system instability or compromise operational integrity [8]. Drawing inspiration from advancements in automotive cybersecurity, this article proposes a strategy to enhance the resilience of maritime electronic control unit (ECU) networks, thereby supporting the operation of modern vessels within an increasingly digitized maritime domain. The cybersecurity challenges associated with cloud-connected maritime systems are examined, with particular emphasis on the vulnerabilities of ECU-based networks. By evaluating known attack vectors, current mitigation techniques, and emerging defense mechanisms, the work aims to establish a comprehensive framework for securing maritime digital infrastructure against evolving cyber threats. Finally, to validate this approach, a low-cost, embedded cloud-connected testbed is implemented. This platform replicates Controller Area Network (CAN) protocol communication and simulates various cyberattack scenarios, enabling practical assessment of potential vulnerabilities and the effectiveness of countermeasures. The paper is organized as follows: Section II defines cybersecurity threats; Section III presents the proposed method; Section IV shows the result of the algorithms, and Section V concludes the paper.

II. CYBERSECURITY VULNERABILITIES

This section highlights possible threats related to the cybersecurity of modern connected shipboard environments. To fully understand the possible risks, it is essential to define when an IoT system is secure in the case of hacker attacks. Key properties of secure communication are:

- **Confidentiality** or secrecy, is the property of being able to prevent a message from being read by an adversary.
- **Integrity** is the property of being able to ensure that a message has not been modified by unauthorized parties.
- **Authentication** is the process or action of verifying the identity of a user or process. That is, if you receive a message you can positively verify that it came from someone who possesses some secret.

Starting with these basic concepts, the main vulnerabilities of the CAN protocol and cloud usage are introduced.

A. CAN protocol weakness

The intention of using the CAN bus is to reduce cost, simplify installation, and improve efficiency for real-time communication. Furthermore, it is resilient to electrical noise and has minimal error detection features, but it is vulnerable to attacks, since when it was invented, security wasn't the main

consideration [9]. Thus, since the CAN bus lacks any security mechanism against cyber attacks, it is possible to recognize some important vulnerabilities:

- **No authentication**
- **No encryption**
- **Priority-based arbitration**
- **Broadcast transmission**

The lack of authentication allows any authorized nodes to join the network and take part in the communication. CAN is a broadcast network thus, there are no source and destination addresses, and every node receives all the messages. Hence, data is not encrypted, and an adversary can observe and steal the data [10]. It also allows a criminal to realize unauthorized access and inject faulty traffic on the system, since it is not possible to determine if a message comes from a malicious node. Moreover, an ECU can make the CAN bus dominant status using the arbitration scheme (Message ID priority scheme) and thus prevent other ECUs from using the bus, which can lead to DOS attack. It is also important to consider the wide attack surface caused by the various external interfaces such as OBD-2, Infotainment USB Ports, Wi-Fi, Bluetooth, NFC, Telematics Units (GPS, Cellular) and GSM. All these connection methodologies make it clear how vulnerable and externally accessible modern interconnected systems are. Table I outlines the most common types of attack targeting the CAN protocol.

B. Key vulnerabilities of cloud use

Despite its operational and economic advantages, cloud computing introduces a range of cybersecurity threats that are particularly critical for safety applications such as shipboard systems. The distributed, multi-tenant nature of cloud environments inherently increases the attack surface and introduces new types of vulnerability. A common model in IoT-based cybersecurity is the CIA triad, which refers to confidentiality,

TABLE I
CAN PROTOCOL CYBER ATTACKS EXPLANATION.

Attack name	Attack description
DOS (Denial-of-Service)	Floods the CAN bus with an excessive number of high-priority frames, thus preventing benign ECUs from transmitting frames that have lower priority.
Fuzzy attack	Involves injecting frames that contain random values across various fields of the CAN frame.
Frame Falsifying Attack	It modifies the CAN message payload by inserting incorrect values. This attack is used to provide an incorrect data payload when the ID is known.
Rate Attack	It changes the frequency of the CAN frames on the bus by modifying the rate of periodic messages.
Sniffing Attack	Without authentication and encryption mechanisms, anyone connected to the CAN bus can acquire the transmitted data.
Suspension Attack	It's designed to stop the transmission of CAN frames originating from a targeted ECU.
Masquerade/ ECU impersonation	It occurs after the suspension of transmission from an ECU. Then, spoofed frames that match the ID, DLC, payload, and timing of the original frames are transmitted, thus seemingly maintaining an unchanged overall traffic pattern.

integrity, and availability [11]. The concepts of confidentiality and integrity have already been introduced regarding the CAN protocol. Instead, availability ensures that IoT systems and services are accessible and operational whenever required by authorized users. In the context of IoT, availability becomes critical due to the real-time and often safety-critical nature of many applications. One of the most prevalent concerns in cloud usage is loss of control over data, especially when sensitive information is managed by third-party providers. This raises significant issues of confidentiality, data ownership, and jurisdiction, especially in multi-national contexts such as global maritime operations. A key issue [12] is that data in the cloud is outsourced to trusted service providers, which compromises the privacy, and then clients often lose direct governance over their own data assets. Another critical threat is account hijacking, which occurs when attackers gain unauthorized access to cloud service credentials. This can lead to full control over cloud services, allowing attackers to manipulate, delete, or steal sensitive data. Even DOS attacks can target cloud infrastructure to disrupt operations. In maritime applications, such attacks could impair access to navigational data or onboard monitoring system. Moreover, [13] many organizations face challenges in applying consistent cybersecurity frameworks due to the variation in provider practices and limited visibility into the cloud infrastructure. These identified threats demonstrate the importance of a tailored cybersecurity approach when integrating cloud services into maritime environments. Starting with these key aspects, this paper has aimed to secure the data exchange between edge devices and the cloud.

III. METHODOLOGY TO MITIGATE THREATS

The main idea of this work is to merge several methods together with the ambition to make the network as secure as possible. By combining different algorithms, it is possible to achieve a more powerful overall system than individual approaches. As soon as an anomaly is detected, it is immediately reported in real time, allowing the problem to be mitigated or precautions to be taken. [14] The intrusion detection developed is composed of rule-based algorithms that perform sequential checks to evaluate whether rules are being followed. A fundamental aspect of the work is the construction of a prototype capable of replicating data traffic representative of a sub-network of CAN nodes. One of the main advantages of this setup lies in its simplicity of implementation and the low cost of the test environment. A real-world system may consist of a large number of ECUs; thus, the network represents a simplified, but still relatable version of a real shipboard environment. The method could be scaled to a more complex scenario. Figure 2 depicts the developed test network consisting of four connected devices communicating via CAN bus used to create a simple but micro-representation of the shipboard ECU connection environment. Specifically, two Raspberry Pi 4 models and two Printed Circuit boards (PCBs) equipped with an Atmega328p microcontroller are used. The CAN protocol has been implemented on the Raspberry Pi

Fig. 2. Schematic representation of components and device connections in our experimental setup.

using the USB to CAN hardware interface, featuring the CAN Controller STM32F0. The Atmega328p microcontroller uses the MCP2515 CAN transceiver for implementing CAN protocol. Both Raspberry Pis have internet access via Wi-Fi, with cloud communication capability. In fact, very often in ships, there is a network-connected ECU (edge) exchanging real-time information with the cloud; therefore, Raspberry Pi has been chosen to simulate the behavior of such a device. In the test setup, one of the two Raspberry Pi is programmed to receive CAN messages and analyze them by running a Python script named *CAN_IDS.py*. This script is responsible for receiving CAN messages in real-time and performing checks to detect anomalies. The other Raspberry Pi performs the function of edge, thus it is the cloud-connected device that can send and receive data via Wi-fi. *Edge_IDS.py* is the python script running on that device, performing real-time network traffic monitoring and anomaly detection using pyshark. The other connected devices are the two PCBs with Atmega328p microcontroller, that are programmed to send CAN messages by simulating a real data exchange. To simulate realistic CAN traffic, a previously recorded CAN message exchange between an automotive three-phase inverter driving a motor and its ECU was used. Two PCBs were programmed to transmit this same set of CAN messages, effectively replicating real CAN traffic. Simultaneously, therefore, two algorithms monitor different aspects of communication, increasing the number of possible anomalies or attacks that can be detected.

To enhance the security of communication with the cloud server, *https* (Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure) has been implemented by generating a self-signed SSL certificate. When accessing the cloud service over *https* address, the server presents a digital certificate to the client to prove its identity and establish a secure, encrypted connection. Therefore, the transition from *http* to *https* ensures that data exchanged over the network is impossible to decode without knowing the secret key. Using the Wireshark tool, the network traffic is inspected, and it has been verified that data transmitted via *https* is encrypted, whereas plaintext data is exposed when using *http*. This certificate must be installed on the edge to enable trusted and encrypted communication with the server,

and in this case, it has been saved on the Raspberry Pi. To send or download data from the cloud, a simple python script runs on the Raspberry Pi and uses the self signed certificate. An interesting aspect of the approach concerns the method of accessing to the test bench. In a real environment, it is often not possible to be physically connected to the node that analyzes traffic, but it is necessary to monitor that device via a remote connection. That condition has been simulated by implementing the SSH (Secure Shell) protocol to connect to the Raspberry Pi and a laptop using PuTTY software. The protocol works according to the client-server model, which means that the connection is established by the SSH client connecting to the SSH server. This protocol uses strong symmetric encryption and hashing algorithms to ensure the privacy and integrity of the data exchanged between the client and the server. Therefore the work has been focused on securing both CAN communication between the various ECUs and also real-time data exchange with the cloud, building on these assumptions.

A. Intrusion Detection Systems for Cyber Attacks

The functions that are executed in the script *CAN_IDS.py* are described in the Table II. A rule-based approach has been implemented where these are checked in cascade, and any violation of one of these conditions causes the anomaly to be reported in the output serial monitor. Cloud communication instead is monitored through the script *Edge_IDS.py* running on the other Raspberry Pi. The functions that are performed in the script *Edge_IDS.py* are described in the Table III .

This algorithm is also a rule-based approach, where a set of rules are checked in sequence, and any violation of one of these conditions causes the anomaly to be reported. In addition to these rules, it has been implemented a simple XOR encryption method with a secret key for one CAN ID. Such

TABLE II
CAN_IDS.py ALGORITHM DESCRIPTION

Function name	Function description
ID_Check	Ensures that the message received has an ID belonging to the list of admissible ones.
DLC_Check	Ensures that the Data Length Code of the received message corresponds to the expected value. The value of allowed DLC is defined for each ID.
Period_Check	For periodic messages, an allowable period value is defined and ensured to be within a threshold. Through the extraction of the message arrival timestamp, the time between messages is calculated.
Suspension_Check	Every 5 seconds is assured that the periodic message counter is incremented for all periodic messages.
Counter_Check	Some messages have a field in the data frame assigned to the counter value; thus, it is ensured that it is incremented correctly on arrival of each message.
Key_Check	Some messages hold a constant secret value in the data frame, thus it is ensured that this value is the predefined one.
Dos_Check	Ensures that no consecutive high-priority messages with ID 0x00 are received.
Sensor_Check	Ensures that the value received of a certain byte of the data frame is within an allowable range for specific messages.

TABLE III
Edge_IDS.py ALGORITHM DESCRIPTION

Function name	Function description
Protocol_Check	Ensures that packets exchanged between edge and server are sent using only through TCP protocol.
Payload_Check	Ensures that the size of packets exchanged between edge and server does not exceed a certain threshold.
Dos_Packet_Check	Ensures that the packets received from edge in a time window does not exceed a certain threshold.

encryption consists of performing a logical XOR between the bits of the data frame and those of a secret key stored in memory. Therefore, if someone is able to sniff those messages, they would still not be able to understand the content without knowing the encryption method and secret decryption key.

IV. RESULTS

To evaluate the performance of the method, cyber attacks have been simulated to test whether or not they are detected. While the attacks are being simulated, the Raspberry Pi is accessed via Putty from a laptop through SSH, allowing the devices to be remotely monitored as well. These attacks have been simulated via Arduino C language scripts that implement a communication that violates one of the rules analyzed by the algorithms. Through these PCBs, it was able to generate the CAN network messages, thus simulating the abnormal behavior. This approach allows for the simulation of many types of hacker attacks in a reversible manner without compromising the operation of the entire system.

A. Cloud communication security tests

First, in Figure 3 it is illustrated that the output on the terminal of *Edge_IDS.py* under nominal traffic conditions, i.e., without any anomaly. In this situation, the algorithm simply shows all the Wi-Fi packets sent and received by the edge. Edge has IP address: 10.240.4.108 and the cloud has IP address: 10.240.36.186. The port on which the information exchange with the cloud takes place instead is 9000. Then, attacks are simulated to test the operation of the algorithm that monitors the communication between the edge and cloud.

Figures 4, 5, and 6 show the output of the algorithm when the anomaly is triggered. As soon as the attack is simulated, the detected anomaly message appears on the Raspberry Pi terminal, thus identifying the potential risk in real time.

```
[09:26:38] TCP 10.240.4.108:43602 → 10.240.36.186:9000
[09:26:38] TCP 10.240.4.108:22 → 10.240.36.186:57177
[09:26:38] TCP 10.240.4.108:22 → 10.240.36.186:57177
[09:26:38] TCP 10.240.36.186:57177 → 10.240.4.108:22
[09:26:38] TCP 10.240.36.186:9000 → 10.240.4.108:43602
[09:26:38] TCP 10.240.4.108:43602 → 10.240.36.186:9000
[09:26:38] TCP 10.240.4.108:43602 → 10.240.36.186:9000
[09:26:38] TCP 10.240.4.108:22 → 10.240.36.186:57177
```

Fig. 3. Output of *Edge_IDS.py* during normal conditions. It displays Timestamp, Protocol, Source IP, Source Port, Destination IP, and Destination Port for all the sniffed packets.

```

[18:20:57] TCP 10.240.4.108:22 → 10.240.36.178:50436
[18:20:57] TCP 10.240.4.108:22 → 10.240.36.178:50436
[18:20:57] HTTP 10.240.36.178:9000 → 10.240.4.108:41094
Protocol Anomaly: HTTP 10.240.36.178:9000 → 10.240.4.108:41094
[18:20:57] HTTP 10.240.4.108:41094 → 10.240.36.178:9000
Protocol Anomaly: HTTP 10.240.4.108:41094 → 10.240.36.178:9000
[18:20:57] TCP 10.240.36.178:50436 → 10.240.4.108:22
[18:20:57] TCP 10.240.4.108:22 → 10.240.36.178:50436

```

Fig. 4. **Protocol attack:** It is simulated by implementing an unsafe *http* protocol communication, through a Python script running on the edge. A cloud file access attempt is made without taking advantage of the self-signed certificate that allows encryption of exchanged data.

```

[10:37:11] TCP 10.240.36.186:9000 → 10.240.4.108:45876
[10:37:11] TCP 10.240.36.186:9000 → 10.240.4.108:45876
[10:37:11] TCP 10.240.4.108:45876 → 10.240.36.186:9000
Payload Anomaly: Downloaded 153.92 kB in 2s
[10:37:11] TCP 10.240.36.186:9000 → 10.240.4.108:45876
[10:37:11] TCP 10.240.36.186:9000 → 10.240.4.108:45876

```

Fig. 5. **Payload attack:** It is simulated by running a Python script that accesses the cloud and downloads a heavy file. Specifically, a maximum download threshold from the cloud of 150 kB every two seconds was set.

```

[11:07:54] TCP 10.240.4.108:22 → 10.240.36.186:57177
[11:07:54] TCP 10.240.36.186:9000 → 10.240.4.108:58410
[11:07:54] TCP 10.240.4.108:22 → 10.240.36.186:57177
DoS Anomaly: 57 packets received in 2 seconds
[11:07:54] TCP 10.240.4.108:58410 → 10.240.36.186:9000
[11:07:54] TCP 10.240.36.186:57177 → 10.240.4.108:22

```

Fig. 6. **DOS attack:** It is simulated through a Python script that accesses the cloud and shows the saved content. This operation is performed at a very high frequency, causing too much packet exchange between the edge and cloud.

B. CAN communication security tests

Under nominal traffic conditions, the script *CAN_IDS.py* simply shows all messages on the CAN bus, and that is shown in Figure 7. This algorithm is independent of the other and only analyzes local CAN transmission between ECUs without being affected by the exchange of packets with the cloud that takes place from the other Raspberry Pi. In the figures 8 to 15 shows the output of the algorithm when the anomalies are triggered. Figure 16 illustrates a special case of anomaly that can also be depicted by a picture since it represents a measure coming from a sensor. At the end, Figure 17 shows the output of the algorithm when the message encoded with ID 0x4f4 is received. Such a message may contain sensitive information that must then be further protected by encryption.

```

Timestamp: 1746448917.1338258 ID: 0xc8 Data: 2a 0 0 0 db 0
Timestamp: 1746448917.1345656 ID: 0xa Data: 3 0 0 0 0
Timestamp: 1746448917.1347728 ID: 0xc9 Data: 63 9 b 0 80 c
Timestamp: 1746448917.135826 ID: 0xc8 Data: 2a 0 0 0 da 0
Timestamp: 1746448917.1365664 ID: 0xa Data: 3 0 0 0 0
Timestamp: 1746448917.1378098 ID: 0xc8 Data: 2a 0 0 0 d6 0
Timestamp: 1746448917.138567 ID: 0xa Data: 3 0 0 0 0
Timestamp: 1746448917.1398273 ID: 0xc8 Data: 2a 0 0 0 da 0

```

Fig. 7. Output of *CAN_IDS.py* during normal conditions. It displays Timestamp, ID and Data frame of CAN messages on the bus.

```

Timestamp: 1746454657.6643991 ID: 0xc8 Data: 2a 0 0 0 da 0
Timestamp: 1746454657.6646066 ID: 0xa Data: 3 0 0 0 0
Timestamp: 1746454657.665133 ID: 0x2f Data: 0 0 5f 56 58 1
Anomaly detected: ID 0x2f is not admissible
Timestamp: 1746454657.666416 ID: 0xc8 Data: 2a 0 0 0 da 0
Timestamp: 1746454657.6666105 ID: 0xa Data: 3 0 0 0 0

```

Fig. 8. **ID attack:** It's simulated by running a script in the PCB that sends an unexpected ID. Here ID 0x2f is unknown, thus it's reported as anomalous.

```

Timestamp: 1746455308.3520384 ID: 0xc8 Data: 2a 0 0 0 db 0
Timestamp: 1746455308.3521998 ID: 0xa Data: 3 0 0 0 0
Timestamp: 1746455308.3536172 ID: 0xca Data: 0 0 5f 56 58 1 ff fa
Anomaly detected: ID 0xca has unexpected DLC: 8 [Nominal value is 6]
Timestamp: 1746455308.35406 ID: 0xa Data: 3 0 0 0 0
Timestamp: 1746455308.3544133 ID: 0xc8 Data: 2a 0 0 0 dd 0

```

Fig. 9. **DLC attack:** It is simulated by running a script in the PCB that sends the ID 0x2f with a wrong Data Length Code.

```

Timestamp: 1746456380.0646837 ID: 0xc8 Data: 2a 0 0 0 d6 0
Timestamp: 1746456380.0649123 ID: 0xa Data: 3 0 0 0 0
Timestamp: 1746456380.0660315 ID: 0xca Data: 0 0 5f 56 58 1
Anomaly detected: ID 0xca Period: 200.02ms out of range [Nominal value: 100.00ms]
Timestamp: 1746456380.066802 ID: 0xc8 Data: 2a 0 0 0 dc 0
Timestamp: 1746456380.0669982 ID: 0xa Data: 3 0 0 0 0

```

Fig. 10. **Period attack:** It is simulated through a script that sends the ID 0xca with a period of 200ms, which is not the admissible value. Specifically it was chosen a tolerance threshold of $[0.5 * NominalPeriod : 1.5 * NominalPeriod]$ has been chosen to consider acceptable values. The period of each ID is calculated by measuring the arrival timestamp of each message.

```

Timestamp: 1746460721.3455472 ID: 0xc8 Data: 2a 0 0 0 d8 0
Timestamp: 1746460721.3460622 ID: 0xa Data: 3 0 0 0 0
Timestamp: 1746460721.347565 ID: 0xc8 Data: 2a 0 0 0 dc 0
Anomaly detected: ID 0xca has not been received in the last 5 seconds
Timestamp: 1746460721.3480656 ID: 0xa Data: 3 0 0 0 0
Timestamp: 1746460721.349579 ID: 0xc8 Data: 2a 0 0 0 da 0

```

Fig. 11. **Suspension attack:** It is simulated by running a script in the PCB that doesn't send the ID 0xca. Then 5 seconds elapsed without receiving such a message, the anomaly is reported.

```

Timestamp: 1746517664.2266111 ID: 0x123 Data: 35 ff 0 d5 8 0 e f5
Timestamp: 1746517664.2277167 ID: 0xa Data: 3 0 0 0 0
Timestamp: 1746517664.227913 ID: 0xc8 Data: 2a 0 0 0 d4 0
Timestamp: 1746517664.2297258 ID: 0xa Data: 3 0 0 0 0
Timestamp: 1746517664.2299159 ID: 0xc8 Data: 2a 0 0 0 d8 0
Timestamp: 1746517664.2306166 ID: 0x123 Data: 36 ff 0 d5 8 0 e f5
Timestamp: 1746517664.231717 ID: 0xa Data: 3 0 0 0 0
Timestamp: 1746517664.2319033 ID: 0xc8 Data: 2a 0 0 0 d4 0
Timestamp: 1746517664.2337222 ID: 0xa Data: 3 0 0 0 0
Timestamp: 1746517664.2339027 ID: 0xc8 Data: 2a 0 0 0 d6 0
Timestamp: 1746517664.2346249 ID: 0x123 Data: 3c ff 0 d5 8 0 e f5
Anomaly detected: ID 0x123 counter value is not correct
Timestamp: 1746517664.235405 ID: 0xc9 Data: 63 9 a 0 80 c

```

Fig. 12. **Counter attack:** It is simulated by running a script in the PCB that sends the ID 0x123 by incorrectly incrementing the counter value within the data frame. Specifically, the image shows how the first byte goes from value 0x36 to value 0x3c instead of 0x37.

```

Timestamp: 1746518583.6682687 ID: 0x123 Data: c7 ff 0 d5 8 0 e f5
Timestamp: 1746518583.6691508 ID: 0xa Data: 3 0 0 0 0
Timestamp: 1746518583.669864 ID: 0xc8 Data: 2a 0 0 0 d9 0
Timestamp: 1746518583.6711478 ID: 0xa Data: 3 0 0 0 0
Timestamp: 1746518583.6718771 ID: 0xc8 Data: 2a 0 0 0 d4 0
Timestamp: 1746518583.6722438 ID: 0x123 Data: c8 a 0 d5 8 0 e f5
Anomaly detected: ID 0x123 key is not correct
Timestamp: 1746518583.6731532 ID: 0xa Data: 3 0 0 0 0

```

Fig. 13. **Secret Key attack:** The simulation is done by running a script in the PCB that sends the ID 0x123, which is the one containing the constant secret key, with an incorrect value. The correct value, located in the second byte of the data frame, is 0xff, and at some point is changed to 0xa.

```

Timestamp: 1746519823.2059228 ID: 0xc8 Data: 2a 0 0 0 d8 0
Timestamp: 1746519823.2067385 ID: 0x123 Data: e0 ff 0 d5 8 0 e 1
Timestamp: 1746519823.2071645 ID: 0x0 Data: 11 0 25 d8
Timestamp: 1746519823.207643 ID: 0x0 Data: 11 0 25 d8
Anomaly detected: DOS attack with ID 0x0
Timestamp: 1746519823.20792 ID: 0xc8 Data: 2a 0 0 0 d8 0
Timestamp: 1746519823.2081044 ID: 0x0 Data: 11 0 25 d8
Anomaly detected: DOS attack with ID 0x0
Timestamp: 1746519823.2085297 ID: 0x0 Data: 11 0 25 d8
Anomaly detected: DOS attack with ID 0x0
Timestamp: 1746519823.2089634 ID: 0x0 Data: 11 0 25 d8
Anomaly detected: DOS attack with ID 0x0

```

Fig. 14. **DOS attack:** The simulation is done by running a script in the PCB that sends the ID 0x00 at high frequency.

```

Timestamp: 1746520923.0955982 ID: 0xc8 Data: 2a 0 0 0 dd 0
Timestamp: 1746520923.0957835 ID: 0xa Data: 3 0 0 0 0 0
Timestamp: 1746520923.0966814 ID: 0x123 Data: 0 ff 0 d5 8 0 e f5
Timestamp: 1746520923.0976 ID: 0xc8 Data: 2a 0 0 0 e6 0
Anomaly detected: ID 0xc8 data[5] value 0xe6 out of range
Timestamp: 1746520923.0977912 ID: 0xa Data: 3 0 0 0 0 0
Timestamp: 1746520923.0995996 ID: 0xc8 Data: 2a 0 0 0 e1 0
Anomaly detected: ID 0xc8 data[5] value 0xe1 out of range
Timestamp: 1746520923.0997906 ID: 0xa Data: 3 0 0 0 0 0

```

Fig. 15. **Sensor Range attack:** The simulation is done by running a script that sends ID 0xc8 with a value of the sixth byte outside a predetermined range. Allowable values for data[5] are between 0xd4 and 0xdd. Such a signal could represent, for example, a voltage measurement coming from a sensor.

Fig. 16. If the value contained in the sixth byte of ID 0xc8 goes out of the range, the anomaly is reported. In this case, the permissible values are between 212 (0xd4) and 221 (0xdd).

```

Timestamp: 1746542015.4768252 ID: 0xc8 Data: 2a 0 0 0 d4 0
Timestamp: 1746542015.4773722 ID: 0x4f4 Data: 6d 67 6f 61
Encrypted message: mgoa Decrypted message: CIAO
Timestamp: 1746542015.478501 ID: 0xa Data: 3 0 0 0 0 0
Timestamp: 1746542015.478818 ID: 0xc8 Data: 2a 0 0 0 dd 0

```

Fig. 17. **Decrypted message:** The corresponding ASCII characters of the data frame, which is shown in hexadecimal, are: 'm' 'g' 'o' 'a'. After decryption, that is, by performing a logical Xor between the bits of the data frame and the secret key = 46, results: 'C' 'I' 'A' 'O'. Therefore, that's an example of how a simple encryption of a single ID in the network can be used to exchange private information without compromising all the remaining messages.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

This work presents an enhanced security method for a ship-board cloud-connected ECU environment. It demonstrates how sequentially applied algorithms can improve safety and detect anomalies. The key strength of this proposed approach is its simplicity and the integration of multiple methods to analyze various communication aspects. The framework allows for expanding the number and complexity of checks to further strengthen its robustness. Designed to be straightforward yet adaptable to more complex scenarios, the method serves as a foundation for future enhancements. Future work will incorporate advanced traffic analysis techniques, including Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning (ML), and fingerprinting, to boost performance, despite increased computational demands on detection. Additionally, the security protocol will be expanded to address new attack scenarios and evaluated for long-term reliability in larger-scale environments.

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